

PERCEIVED BENEFITS AND BARRIERS OF CONTINUING PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT: IT'S LINK TO ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT AMONG POLICE NURSES OF BANGSAMORO AUTONOMOUS REGION

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ABSTRACT

The objective of the study is to determine Police Nurses' perception of continuing professional development and its link to organizational commitment. A correlational research design was utilized in the study. Data were gathered using a Google forms-based survey questionnaire. Respondents of the study were the Police Nurses (50) from Philippine National Police. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Pearson – r to test the relationships among variables. The findings of the study indicated that Police Nurses perceived some benefits and barriers in engaging with continuing professional development. That Police Nurses face challenges on retaining and participating in CPD. Also, Police Nurses must improve their skills and knowledge to keep up with the slow revolution in medical technology and the wide range of healthcare needs, with overall mean ranging from 3.00 to 3.06 on the different domains, respectively. The study also showed a moderate level of organizational commitment among the respondents. Furthermore, Police Nurses display a passionate connection to their organization, show positive outcomes in were they mostly agree to stay within the organization, and show ethical commitment towards their organization, with the computed Pearson-r of 0.489 a significant correlation between the perceptions of continuing professional development and organizational commitment was revealed in the study. Continuing professional development is essential for Police Nurses and can help them achieve their objective of efficiently protecting and serving the public. The formulation of new guidelines and policies is suggested to support the professional development of Police Nurses strongly.

Keywords: *Continuing Professional Development, Organizational Commitment, Police Nurse*

INTRODUCTION

Internationally and locally, nurses continue to have serious concerns about continuing professional development. The CPD law's primary goal is to advance and raise the level of professionalism held by Filipinos in the country as a whole (Palma et al., 2022). It is a mandate that Filipino professionals must meet in order to advance their abilities, values, and knowledge. The requirement for professional development is increased by the updating of professional qualifications (Cervantes, 2022). The Philippines' urgent need to move toward ASEAN harmonization and globalization is one of the factors propelling CPD implementation. Integrating the professional competencies and credentials of Filipinos with global standards and procedures is necessary to preserve global competitiveness (Crispino & Rocha, 2021).

High organizational commitment in nurses was defined as having a strong enough attachment to or bond with their organizations to keep them in their current positions. Demonstrating dedication involves showing loyalty and commitment to sustain a relationship with one's organization despite challenges. Nurses who are dedicated to their sworn duties and responsibilities can deliver high-quality services that meet holistic standards. Given the growing nursing shortage throughout the world, nurses must continue to be dedicated to their organizations. High organizational commitment among nurses promotes a long-lasting workforce that keeps both new and seasoned nurses (Al-Oweidat et al., 2023).

The nursing profession plays a crucial role in society, serving as a cornerstone for healthcare delivery and maintaining high health standards, with nursing staff being indispensable. The well-being of this critical societal sector is directly related to nurses' organizational commitment, which, in turn, is essential for patient safety (Salem et al., 2016). According to the study of Sepahvand et al. (2017), a moderate level of organizational dedication among nurses highlights a noteworthy and positive link between the continuance of organizational commitment and factors such as years of experience, staff positions, and work shifts. The development level of nursing staff stands as a vital element within the healthcare system, potentially influencing the quality of care delivered. However, a prior study conducted by Vasquez et al. (2020) discovered that a crucial topic that needs to receive more attention is nurses' experiences with CPD.

To support the vital need for continuing professional development among police nurses, this study explored the police nurses' perceptions of continuing professional development and its link to organizational commitment. Continuing Professional Development is "a lifelong process of active participation by nurses in learning activities that assist in developing and maintaining their continuing competence, enhancing professional practice, and supporting the achievement of their professional goals" (American Nurses Association, 2015).

Due to the preceding concerns about professional development and organizational commitment among Police Nurses, the researcher was prompted to conduct this study to be able to contribute more to the new body of knowledge and literature. Gaining a thorough insight into nurses' perception of continuing professional development and their level of commitment to the organization is crucial, providing a foundation for the implementation of suitable interventions.

Research Questions

This study was conducted to determine the police nurses' perception on continuing professional development in relation to organizational commitment. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. How is continuing professional development as perceived among the respondents described in terms of:
 - 1.1 Benefits
 - 1.2 Barriers
 - 1.3 Reasons

2. How is the level of organizational commitment described among the respondents in terms of the following:
 - 2.1 Affective
 - 2.2 Continuous
 - 2.3 Normative

3. Is the perception of continuing professional development and organizational commitment significantly correlated?

4. What is the implication of the study to police administration?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a descriptive correlational research design aimed at establishing a relationship between two closely associated topics or variables. It is a non-experimental research design type that requires at least two groups of data (Thakur, 2021). Hence, the study used this research design to investigate the correlation between Police Nurses' perceptions of Continuing Professional Development (CPD) and their organizational commitment. The study's respondents were the Police Nurses who are assigned to the Regional Medical and Dental Unit Bangsamoro Autonomous Region (RMDU BAR). They were selected utilizing a purposive sampling technique based on given criteria: educational attainment, medical training, and length of service. A total of 50 police nurses are presently assigned from the medical unit participated in this study.

A questionnaire was used for the collection of data that consisted of three parts. The initial part centered on the participants' profiles. The second part seeks questions on

continuing professional development. In this section, a designed survey by Ihudiebube-Splendor et al. (2017) was adapted and utilized. The third part addresses organizational commitment, which was measured using the revised version of the three-component model questionnaire created by Meyer and Allen (1997). A Likert-type scale (4 = strongly agree to 1 = strongly disagree) was utilized for each item.

This study centered on exploring the perception of Police Nurses' Continuing Professional Development (CPD) in connection with organizational commitment. The collected data were tabulated and used descriptive statistics such as frequency count, percentage and mean, and also with the use inferential statistics such as Pearson-r correlation utilized for analyzing the data. Ethical principle was observed and informed consent was acquired from the participants. Respondents were limited to graduates of Bachelor of Science in Nursing presently assigned at the Regional Medical and Dental Unit Bangsamoro Autonomous Region. The period of the study was 2023-2024.

RESULTS

Table 1 shows the age range of the respondents from 25 to 55 and above. The respondents are mostly 25–34 years old, with a frequency of 29 or 58%.

Table 1. Age of the Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
25-34	29	58%
35-44	19	38%
45-54	2	4%
Total	50	100%

Table 2 indicates that there is an equal distribution of the respondents as to gender, which is 25 or 50%, respectively.

Table 2. Gender of the Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	25	50%
Female	25	50%
Total	50	100%

Table 3 shows that the perception of benefits obtained an overall mean of 3.06, with a verbal description of agreement. It also indicates that the statement with the highest mean of 3.12 with a verbal description of agreement is "CPD participation enables the nurse to provide improved patients' care." Statements 7, 8, 9, and 10 obtained the lowest mean of 3.04 with a verbal description of agree.

Table 3. Perception in terms of Benefits

Statements	Mean	Verbal Description
1. CPD participation enables the nurse to provide improved patients' care.	3.12	Agree
2. Participation in CPD enhances the knowledge base of nurses.	3.08	Agree
3. CPD increases self-confidence and self-esteem.	3.06	Agree
4. CPD maintains professional competence.	3.06	Agree
5. CPD enables the nurse to contribute to the development of Nursing.	3.06	Agree
6. CPD participation assists nurses to meet various needs of patients.	3.06	Agree
7. CPD improves job performance.	3.04	Agree
8. CPD enables the nurse to evaluate his/her own area of practice.	3.04	Agree
9. CPD improves nurses' clinical leadership skills.	3.04	Agree
10. Participation in CPD helps in developing skills/techniques in nursing care.	3.04	Agree
Overall Mean	3.06	Agree

Table 4 indicates that the barriers to CPD among Police Nurses obtain an overall mean of 3.00 with a verbal description of Agree. The highest mean of 3.16, with a verbal description of agreement, is found in the statements "Lack of financial support to fund or go on CPD courses at the desirable time" and "Lack of learning facilities near to place of residence." The lowest mean of 2.84 with a verbal description of agree is with the statement, "Lack of a supportive work environment due to colleagues' refusal to sit in for one's absence."

Table 4. Perception in terms of Barriers

Statement	Mean	Verbal Description
1. Lack of financial support to fund or go on CPD courses at the desirable time.	3.16	Agree
2. Lack of learning facilities near to place of residence.	3.16	Agree
3. Too much workload.	3.12	Agree

4. Lack of early notification of the program.	2.98	Agree
5. Unavailability of appropriate program that is relevant for nurses to clinical practice needs.	2.98	Agree
6. Lack of opportunities to utilize new skills in workplace.	2.98	Agree
7. Lack of employer's co-operation to allow time away from the workplace.	2.96	Agree
8. Family and child care responsibilities which deter one from active participation in the CPD program.	2.92	Agree
9. Date and time that is scheduled for the program is inappropriate.	2.90	Agree
10. Lack of a supportive work environment due to colleagues' refusal to sit in for one's absence.	2.84	Agree
Overall Mean	3.00	Agree

Table 5 shows that perception in terms of reason obtains an overall mean of 3.05, with a verbal description of agreement. The statement with the highest mean of 3.14, with a verbal description of agreeing, is "To be more critical in providing care." The statement with the lowest mean of 2.86, with a verbal description of agreeing, is "To provide a break from the pressures of work."

Table 5. Perception in terms of Reasons

Statement	Mean	Verbal Description
1. To be more critical in providing care.	3.14	Agree
2. To improve confidence.	3.10	Agree
3. To develop proficiency necessary to meet patients' expectations.	3.08	Agree
4. To improve my management skills.	3.08	Agree
5. To improve my decision making skills.	3.08	Agree
6. To obtain knowledge to achieve professional status.	3.08	Agree
7. To develop leadership capabilities.	3.04	Agree
8. To plan my career.	3.04	Agree
9. To gain knowledge and skills not obtained during that basic training.	3.02	Agree
10. To provide a break from the pressures of work.	2.86	Agree
Overall Mean	3.05	Agree

Table 6 indicates the affective level of organizational commitment, obtaining an overall mean of 2.80 with a verbal description of Agree. The data below also indicates the highest mean of 3.02, with a verbal description of agreement in the statement, "I would be happy to spend the rest of my career with this organization." The lowest mean of 2.52, with a verbal description of agreeing, is found in the statement, "I really feel as if this organization's problems are my own."

Table 6. Affective Organizational Commitment

Statement	Mean	Verbal Description
1. I would be very happy to spend the rest of my career with this organization.	3.02	Agree
2. This organization has a great deal of personal meaning for me.	2.96	Agree
3. I feel like "part of the family" in my organization.	2.88	Agree
4. I am "emotionally attached" at work	2.76	Agree
5. I feel accepted by everyone.	2.68	Agree
6. I really feel as if this organization's problems are my own.	2.52	Agree
Overall mean	2.80	Agree

Table 7 shows that a continuous level of organizational commitment obtains an overall mean of 2.65 with a verbal description of Agree. The statement with the highest mean of 2.76 with a verbal description of agreement is "staying in the organization right now is a matter of necessity." The statement with the lowest mean of 2.50 and a verbal description of agreement is "If I had already put so much of myself into this organization, I might consider working elsewhere."

Table 7. Continuous Organizational Commitment

Statement	Mean	Verbal Description
1. Staying in the organization right now is a matter of necessity	2.76	Agree
2. My life would be disrupted if I leave my organization now.	2.70	Agree
3. Scarcity of available alternatives would be one of the consequences of leaving this organization.	2.66	Agree
4. It would be very hard for me to leave my organization right now	2.64	Agree
5. I feel that I few options to consider leaving my present job.	2.64	Agree
6. If I had already put so much of myself into this organization, I might consider working elsewhere.	2.50	Agree
Overall Mean	2.65	Agree

Table 8 shows that the normative level of organizational commitment among Police Nurses obtains an overall mean of 2.95 with a verbal description of Agree. It also illuminates that the statement with the highest mean of 3.12 with a verbal description of agreement is “I owe a great deal to my organization.” The statement with the lowest mean of 2.70 and verbal description of agreement is “I will feel guilty if I leave my organization now.”

Table 8. Normative Organizational Commitment

Statement	Mean	Verbal Description
1. I owe a great deal to my organization.	3.12	Agree
2. I have my loyalty to the organization	3.08	Agree
3. I have an obligation to stay with my current employer.	3.02	Agree
4. I would not leave my organization right now because I feel a sense of obligation to the people in it.	2.94	Agree
5. Even if it were to my advantage, I do not feel it would be right to leave my organization now.	2.84	Agree
6. I will feel guilty if I leave my organization now.	2.70	Agree
Overall Mean	2.95	Agree

Table 9 indicates that organizational commitment and perception on continuing professional development have significant relationship since the computed Pearson-r of 0.489 is higher than the p-value of 0.000 correlations is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). Which also leads to the decision to reject the null hypothesis.

Table 9. Overall Correlation between Organizational Commitment and Perception on Continuing Professional Development

Pearson <i>r</i>	<i>p</i> -value	Decision	Result
0.489	0.000	Reject H ₀	Significant

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study showed that the respondents predominantly agreed with the statements regarding the CPD domains. Police Nurses can benefit from CPD but face challenges such as these barriers to retaining and participating in CPD. They must improve their skills and knowledge to keep up with the slow revolution in medical technology and the wide range of healthcare needs. However, the result of this is supported by several studies. In the study of Draper & Clark (2016), it was found that participants showed signs of a lack of organizational support—especially from managers—it was assumed that the organization did not value professional development. A few of the stated barriers to CPD were heavy workloads, inadequate study time, poor

funding, and low personnel levels. This also validates the research conducted by Yu et al. (2022) found that nurses had adopted the initiative to seek self-development by using a variety of resources. Given the notable transformations in the field of nursing, it has become essential for nurses to uphold competency standards and provide top-notch patient care by fostering their drive and motivation in clinical practice. Police Nurses' perceptions of continuing professional development (CPD) were found to be beneficial, which contributed to the study's positive outcome.

The findings of this study revealed a moderate affective commitment among Police Nurses. This means that Police Nurses' affective level of commitment to the organization demonstrates a strong emotional attachment to their organization, a keen aspiration for the organization's success, and takes pride in being a member of the organization. This finding is congruent with the study of Labrague et al. (2018), which affirms that nurses were found to have "moderate commitment" with higher scores on the affective commitment subscale, indicating that the nurses had a solid emotional bond with their employer.

The findings of this study showed a moderate continuous commitment among Police Nurses. The result is aligned with the findings of Johnson et al. (2015), wherein nurses expressed in the continuance domain that leaving their organization would put them at a disadvantage. Due to their degree of attachment or connection, nurses exhibited a reduced inclination to depart from their organization and a greater readiness to remain. Police Nurses' continuous level of commitment to the organization shows positive outcomes in which they mainly agreed to stay within the organization rather than embracing other avenues.

The findings of this study on the normative level of organizational commitment are supported by several studies that also showed that nurses demonstrated a moderate level of commitment (Poochangizi et al., 2017; Timalisina et al., 2018; Labrague et al., 2018). The findings of this study exhibited a moderate continuous commitment among Police Nurses. Hence, the normative commitment level among Police Nurses demonstrates their ethical dedication to the organization, indicating a significant sense of obligation towards it.

Police Nurses who actively participate in Continuing Professional Development (CPD) also demonstrate a profound commitment to their organization. Views on continuing professional development are favorable. Continuous professional development was recognized to have a crucial role in an organization's focus on gradual but ongoing practice development (Averlid, 2017). It is therefore believed that continuing professional development is a requisite for Police Nurses and can help them achieve their objective of efficiently protecting and serving the public. Police Nurses must concentrate on improving their knowledge, abilities, and attitudes through constant education and training in order to implement and be carried out by the police workforce.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that Police Nurses' continuing professional development is essential to maintain their competency in both professional policing and nursing practice. The Police Nurses faced significant challenges to CPD participation and exhibited a moderate degree of organizational commitment. Police nurse's perceptions of continuing professional development and commitment to the organization significantly influence each other.

Recommendations

To the Philippine National Police Administration may review its strategic focus on developing and implementing continuing education. Arrange for suitable CPD training and seminars that are accessible in time, place, financially and provide avenues to utilize new skills in the workplace for Police Nurses. Policymakers ought to regularly evaluate the quality of training providers, both domestic and foreign and CPD providers may offer a variety of incentives to support Police Nurses in fulfilling their CPD requirements. Lastly, to future researchers, conduct further studies utilizing other research methods and a larger sample size, explore other factors that influence the importance of CPD, and determine aspects that contribute to the commitment to the organization.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Throughout the study, the ethical principle was observed. Before the distribution of questionnaires, a letter of disclosure about the study was issued in order for them to comprehend the purpose of the study and be aware of the question that was asked. Subsequently, participants were asked for their consent and to take part voluntarily without fear of consequences, giving them the option to withdraw anytime during the duration of the study. All information collected for this study was kept secure and confidential. The participants' privacy was highly respected, and they stayed anonymous. Results were utilized exclusively for research purposes, and after the researcher had completed collecting, tabulating, and analyzing the data, all research information from the participants was obliterated.

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REFERENCES

- Al-Oweidat, I., Shosha, G.A., Baker, T.A. (2023). The relationship between emotional intelligence and organizational commitment among nurses working in governmental hospitals in Jordan. *BMC Nursing* 22, 195
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-023-01361-2>
- American Nurses Association and National Nursing Staff Development Organization. (2015) *Nursing professional development: scope and standards of practice*: SilverSpring,MD.Nursesbooks.org.<https://www.nursingworld.org/~4af71a/globalassets/catalog/book-toc/nssp3e-sample-chapter.pdf>
- Averlid, R. N. A. (2017). Norwegian nurse anesthetist perceptions of professional development and the influence of production pressure. *AANA journal*, 85(5), 345. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/320441270>
- Cervantes, F. M. (2022). House OKs bill amending CPD law on final reading. *Philippine News Agency*. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1175679> Philippine Business School.
- Clark E, Draper J, Rogers J. (2015). Illuminating the process: enhancing the impact of continuing professional education on practice. *Nurse Education Today*.35(2):388–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2014.10.014>.
- Crispino, Kevin T. and Rocha, Ian Christopher N. (2021). Enhancing Healthcare Professional Practice in the Philippines toward ASEAN Integration through the Continuing Professional Development Law. *ASEAN Journal of Community Engagement*. 5(2), 376-395. <https://doi.org/10.7454/ajce.v5i2.1141>
- Draper J, and Clark L. (2016). Managers' role in maximising investment in continuing professional education. *Nurse Manager*. 22(9):30–6. <https://doi:10.7748/nm.22.9.30.s29>
- Ihudiebube-Splendor, C. N., Odikpo, L. C., Ogwu, J. O., Chinweuba, A. U., & Osuala, E. O. (2017). Mandatory continuing education for professional development program: Perceptions of Nurses in university of nigeria teaching hospital Ituku-Ozalla, Enugu State Nigeria. *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)*, 6(5), 2190- 2195. <https://DOI: 10.21275/ART20173403>
- Johnson J, Brennan M, Musil C, Fitzpatrick J. (2015). Practice patterns and organizational commitment of inpatient nurse practitioners. *Journal of the American Association Nurse Practitioners*. 28(7):370–8. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2327-6924.12318>
- Labrague LJ., McEnroe-Petitte DM., Tsaras K., Cruz JP., Colet PC., Gloe DS. (2018). Organizational commitment and turnover intention among rural nurses in the

- Philippines: Implications for nursing management. *International Journal of Nursing Sciences*, 5(4), 403-408. [https://doi: 10.1016/j.ijnss.2018.09.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnss.2018.09.001).
- Meyer, J. P., & Allen, N. J. (1997). *Commitment in the workplace: Theory, research, and application*. Sage Publications.
- Palma, J. A. F. S., Oducado, R. M. F., & Palma, B. S. (2020). Continuing professional cridevelopment: Awareness, attitude, facilitators, and barriers among nurses in the Philippines. *Nursing Practice Today*, 7(3), 198-207. [https://doi:10.18502/npt.v7i3.3348](https://doi.org/10.18502/npt.v7i3.3348)
- Poorchangizi, B., Farokhzadian, J., Abbaszadeh, A. (2017). The importance of professional values from clinical nurses' perspective in hospitals of a medical university in Iran. *BMC Medical Ethics*, 18(20). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12910-017-0178-9>.
- Salem, O. A., Baddar, F., & AL-Mugatti, H. M. (2016). Relationship between Nurses Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment. *Journal of Nursing and Health Science*, 5(1), 49-55. [https://DOI: 10.9790/1959-05114955](https://DOI:10.9790/1959-05114955).
- Sepahvand F., Atashzadeh-Shoorideh F., Parvizy S., Tafreshi M.Z. (2017). The relationship between some demographic characteristics and organizational commitment of nurses working in the Social Security Hospital of Khorramabad. *Electron Physician*, 9(6), 4503–4509. [https://doi: 10.19082/4503](https://doi.org/10.19082/4503).
- Thakur, H. K. (2021). *Research Methodology in Social Science: A Short Manual*. Covette Press. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/353430802_Research_Design
- Timalsina, R., KC, S., Rai, N., & Chhantyal, A. (2018). Predictors of organizational commitment among university nursing Faculty of Kathmandu Valley, Nepal. *BMC Nursing*, 17(30): 1-8. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1186/s12912-018-0298-7>
- Vasquez-Calatayud M., Errasti-Ibarrondo B., Choperena A. (2020). Nurses' Continuing Professional Development: A Systematic Literature Review. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 50:102963. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2020.102963>
- Yu, X., Huang, Y. & Liu, Y. (2022). Nurses' perceptions of continuing professional development: a qualitative study. *BMC Nursing* 21, 162 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-022-00940>